

EDEN ISS

CFD Simulations Report

prepared for

WP 2.4 – Thermal Fluid Dynamic & Environmental Simulations

Version: 2.1

Published: 2017-09-19

Approved by:	Erik Mazzoleni	ES	Work Package Leader
Approved by:	Matthew Bamsey	DLR	Systems Engineer
Approved by:	Daniel Schubert	DLR	Project Manager

List of Authors:

Participant No.	Short name	Author name(s)
1	ES	D. Magnabosco, E. Mazzoleni, L. Bucchieri

Document Change Log:

Version	Date	Author name(s)	Description of Change
0.1	2015-12-11	D. Magnabosco	Draft
1.0	2016-02-10	D. Magnabosco, E.Mazzoleni, L.Bucchieri	Draft
2.0	2017-06-21	D. Magnabosco, E.Mazzoleni, L.Bucchieri	First full release
2.1	2017-09-19	V. Vrakking	Final release

Table of contents

Table of contents 3

Acronyms 4

1 Introduction..... 5

2 Design Status / Executive Summary..... 6

3 Supply Air Channels 7

 3.1 Rigid and Flexible Ducts9

 3.1.1 Geometry, mesh and boundary conditions..... 9

 3.1.2 Results 15

 3.2 Single horizontal duct..... 20

 3.2.1 Geometrical configurations..... 20

 3.2.2 Results 22

4 AMS Rack..... 24

 4.1 Initial Configuration..... 25

 4.1.1 Geometry, mesh and boundary conditions..... 25

 4.1.2 Results 29

 4.2 Updated configuration 30

 4.2.1 Geometry, mesh and boundary conditions..... 30

 4.2.2 Results 31

5 Future Exploration Greenhouse..... 33

 5.1 Summer day – with plants..... 34

 5.1.1 Geometry and mesh 34

 5.1.2 Physical model and boundary conditions..... 36

 5.1.3 Results 41

 5.2 Summer day – without plants 50

 5.3 Winter night 51

 5.3.1 Boundary conditions..... 51

6 Failure scenario for the Mobile Test Facility..... 53

 6.1 Geometry and mesh..... 53

 6.2 Physical model and boundary conditions 54

 6.3 Results 55

7 Conclusions..... 57

References..... 58

Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation	Acronym	Explanation
AMS	Air Management System	FEG	Future Exploration Greenhouse
AS	Aero Sekur S.p.A.	HTC	Heat Transfer Coefficient
AWI	Alfred Wegener Institute	MTF	Mobile Test Facility
CE	Concurrent Engineering	NM-III	Neumayer Station III
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamic	RH	Relative humidity
DLR	German Aerospace Center	VOC	Volatile Organic Compounds
ES	EnginSoft S.p.A.		

1 Introduction

The following document presents a summary of the CFD simulations performed by EnginSoft S.p.A. to improve the design of the MTF. The development of the internal layout began during the CE study at DLR Institute of Space System from September 7th to September 18th 2015 and was documented in the Design Report [4].

An iterative approach was applied for all the systems considered, improving the models step by step towards the optimum solution. Several iterations were performed for each sub-system, where the modifications were suggested from the results of a baseline simulation, with considerations regarding the costs and the feasibility of the new configurations. In this process ES worked in close collaboration with DLR and AS.

This report is focused on thermal, fluid dynamic and environmental analyses, considering the impact of both internal and external variables on systems design.

In particular, attention has been paid to the simulation of the AMS which has a key role in conditioning the FEG atmosphere and ensuring the comfort of the plants. For this reason specific simulations have been performed on the AMS unit and supply ducts (described in chapter 3 and 4), and also on the environmental conditions in the FEG (chapter 5). The influence of environmental conditions on the thermal stability of the MTF has also been taken into account (chapter 6).

A detailed description of the content of each chapter is summarized below.

In chapter 3, the supply air channels are considered and optimized in order to improve their performance, in terms of mass flow balance and pressure losses. In section 3.1 a comparison between the original geometry, with rigid ducts, and another option with flexible ducts is performed. Starting from the results obtained in these simulations, a detailed optimization of the geometry of the horizontal duct is analyzed. The optimization aims to ensure the mass flow distribution is balanced among the louvers to ensure the same amount of fresh air on each plant, while considering manufacturing complexity and cost.

In chapter 4, the sub-system which is dedicated to the air treatment is studied, showing the pressure losses of each component of the AMS Rack. Considerations about the target mass flow and the fan selection come out from this analysis.

The entire FEG is modeled in chapter 5, giving evidence of stagnation areas, non-uniform thermal distribution and stratification. In this section the “summer day” condition is modeled, showing a worst case scenario that can happen during the operating period in Antarctica. A modification of the design is proposed and simulated to achieve a better temperature distribution.

Finally, transient simulations are performed and summarized in chapter 6 to evaluate the effect of external environmental conditions when the MTF is in a failure scenario. In case of a break down, the simulations compute how long the internal temperature takes to reach a specified limit.

All the simulations described in this report have been carried out using ANSYS CFD software: SpaceClaim for geometrical de-featuring, ICEM CFD for mesh generation, CFX for numerical settings and solution computation, and finally CFD Post for post processing [8].

2 Design Status / Executive Summary

This chapter provides an overview of the latest design status of the systems which have been involved in the simulation process. In particular the last simulation results and key decisions are summarized below.

Supply air channels (chapter 3)

- The supply ducts are composed of flexible ducts and internal valves. This solution allows a direct control on the mass flow split among the 8 horizontal ducts.
- The total pressure loss of the supply air channels with flexible ducts is 422 Pa.
- The area on the louvers section has been increased from the initial design to reduce velocity near the plants.
- A variable width for each horizontal channel has been defined. The width of the channel is reduced going far from the inflow section. This solution produces a better balance of the flow among the louvers.

AMS Rack (chapter 4)

- The initial design had a geometry which resulted in excessive pressure losses, which prevented the AMS subsystem from reaching the target flow rate. A design change was implemented to reduce the geometric pressure losses.
- The total pressure losses of the AMS loop are 2035 Pa in the worst case scenario, when the filters are clogged. This pressure loss occurs at the working point, where pressure losses are balanced against the fan pressure head.
- The flow rate provided by the fans in this worst case scenario is 1458 m³/h, which meets the requirement of 1400 m³/h.

FEG (chapter 5)

- The FEG is simulated in a worst case scenario: “summer day” condition has been considered, i.e. when all the LEDs are on and the external temperature is 5 °C.
- 8 tangential fans are introduced to modify the original baseline layout. Fans are mounted on the ceiling and blow hot air downward. With these internal fans, the air is generally better mixed with a relevant reduction of gradients for temperature and RH.
- RH reaches 100% when all of the plants are fully grown. To avoid this, air should enter the FEG with a RH < 70%.

Failure scenario for MTF (chapter 6)

- The cooling time of the MTF from 22°C to 5 °C has been calculated, taking into account different environmental conditions.
- Wind speed has a low influence on the cooling time for MTF: this is due to the low value of HTC for the isolating material.
- Wind temperature has a relevant influence on the cooling time for MTF. With an external temperature of -10 °C, the cooling time of the MTF (from 22 °C to 5 °C) is around 3 hours.

3 Supply Air Channels

The objective of this study is to optimize the shape of the supply air channels in order to obtain an approximately equal flow distribution at all plant trays within the FEG.

In a first step the entire system is considered, as shown in Figure 1. The system starts with one single duct (flow section= 0.168m x 0.698m, Figure 2 Left) which splits into two branches (Figure 2-Right), left and right. This part is positioned in the Service Section, under the floor. Each branch splits again into 4 ducts each (Figure 3-Left). These horizontal ducts enter the FEG and pass next to the side walls to reach the trays of the plants. With this system, air is distributed along the plants and is collected by a return duct positioned at the top of the FEG (Figure 3 Right). In section 3.1, two solutions are proposed and compared, called rigid and flexible ducts.

Figure 1 Supply Air Channel

Figure 2 Left: first single duct. Right: the first duct splits in 2 branches

Figure 3 Left: Each branch splits in 4 horizontal ducts Right: outflow duct

In a second step, one of the 8 horizontal ducts is studied, since a single duct is representative of all ducts, to focus on air distribution among the louvers. Several geometrical solutions are analyzed to reach a uniform flow through the louvers. These solutions are described in section 3.2.

The optimization process aims to have an adequate mass flow distribution, respecting the following guidelines:

- At each branch of the system, the flow should be split equally in order to avoid imbalance among channels
- The maximum velocity near the crops should not be too high. For this reason the penetration of the stream into the FEG is also pointed out.
- The distribution along the louvers should be uniform in order to maintain all the crops at the same conditions.

3.1 Rigid and Flexible Ducts

3.1.1 Geometry, mesh and boundary conditions

Figure 4 Comparison between rigid (left) and flexible (right) ducts

In this section a comparison is made between the rigid and flexible ducts represented in Figure 4. The only part that changes is the connection with the four horizontal ducts. On one hand, there are 4 rigid tubes for each side; on the other hand, there are 8 flexible tubes (in blue) for each side with the addition of 8 valves with one for each tube (in red). These valves allow a regulation of the flow, in order to have a uniform distribution in each channel. Moreover, the flexible ducts are easier to build and assemble.

The geometry analysed in this simulation is reported in Figure 5. A few modifications are performed to simplify the model and the fluid volume is extracted.

Figure 5 Fluid volume of rigid ducts (left) and flexible ducts (right)

The meshing procedure leads to a tetra-prism mesh of 21 million elements for both geometries. Prisms are added on the walls to capture the boundary layer and a refinement is done at the ducts openings (Figure 6).

Figure 6 Mesh of rigid ducts (left) and flexible ducts (right)

Figure 7 Boundary conditions for rigid ducts

The following boundary conditions are set, referring to Figure 7, which apply for both configurations:

- Fixed temperature = 20 °C
- Inlet: mass flow = 1400 m³/h
- Outlet: static pressure = 1 atm
- Channel Walls: no slip
- Wall at the entrance: free slip

In the simulation with flexible ducts, the valves are modeled as porous media with a momentum loss. The curve of the valve is reported in Figure 8 [1]. Both simulations are carried out in steady state condition, considering a turbulent flow.

Figure 8 Valve curve (pressure loss over velocity)

Virtual monitor planes are added in order to check pressure and mass flow. They are positioned at the branches of the ducts and at the channel outlet. With these monitors, 3 splits of the flow are identified as follows:

- Split 1: The main channel is divided into 2 channels (left and right) as in Figure 9 (Green arrows). One monitor is positioned at the single main duct and 2 monitors are at the 2 branches, left and right (blue section in the figure). This identifies the pressure loss due to the first split and it is computed as the pressure difference after and before the split: ΔP_1 . Also, the mass flow is computed at the blue surface to check if the flow is split equally across the left and right branch.

Figure 9 Split 1

- Split 2: Each side channel is divided into 4 channels as in Figure 10 for the rigid ducts (orange arrows). 4 monitors for each side are positioned at the horizontal ducts, after the separation and one monitor before. Therefore the pressure drop ΔP_2 is calculated as the difference after and before

the branch. Also in this case the mass flow at the blue surfaces is monitored to check an equal flow subdivision. Analogously, for the configuration with flexible ducts in Figure 11, at Split 2, 8 flexible tubes start from each side and the monitors are set at the corresponding position. In this case another subdivision is done in the computation of the pressure drop, since there are the valves that give an additional contribution. ΔP_{2b} is computed after and before the valves, while ΔP_2 is the loss due to the geometric contribution of the ducts.

Figure 10 Split 2 in rigid ducts

Figure 11 Split 2 in flexible ducts

- Split 3: The flow exiting the channels is split into main side openings and small openings on the top and bottom. The main openings correspond to the louvers, green in Figure 12. The small openings, red in the figure, are positioned at the bottom and top part of the channel, to blow air near the FEG walls and prevent possible condensation effects. The mass flow is monitored at these surfaces. The pressure drop ΔP_3 in Figure 13 is computed after and before these outlets, i.e. the pressure at the suction duct minus the pressure at the beginning of the horizontal channels.

Figure 12 Small Opening in red (up and down). Main opening in green (numbered from 1 to 8)

Figure 13 Pressure drop at split 3

3.1.2 Results

This section presents the results for both configurations, pointing out the analogies and differences.

The mass flow split is checked at the branching locations. In the following tables the percentages are reported at the different splits. Regarding the splits number 1 and 2, collected in Table 1 and Table 2, the flow is divided uniformly. On the contrary at the channel openings (Table 3 and Table 4), the distribution is not balanced, ranging from -0.7% to 7.8%. A few louvers close to the supply section (numbered with 1) suck air from the FEG into the channel, and louvers near the end of the supply duct blow a large amount of air (compared to the other louvers) into the FEG. This behavior affects both configurations.

Table 1 Split 1

	RIGID	FLEXIBLE
left	52.30%	50.11%
right	47.70%	49.89%
Total	100.00%	100.00%

Table 2 Split 2 Left and Right

	RIGID			FLEXIBLE	
	left	right		left	right
Channel1	26.85%	27.67%	Channel1	12.21%	12.24%
Channel2	27.05%	24.98%	Channel2	12.36%	12.66%
Channel3	23.53%	21.83%	Channel3	12.46%	12.55%
Channel4	22.57%	25.52%	Channel4	12.49%	12.28%
			Channel5	12.46%	12.47%
			Channel6	12.75%	12.56%
			Channel7	12.73%	12.65%
			Channel8	12.54%	12.59%
Total	100.00%	100.00%	Total	100.00%	100.00%

Table 3 Split 3 Left

RIGID											
	Main openings								Small openings		
left	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	up	down	Total
Channel1	0.83%	1.15%	1.30%	1.61%	2.37%	3.83%	6.10%	7.00%	1.50%	1.25%	26.93%
Channel2	0.17%	1.51%	1.48%	1.75%	2.24%	3.48%	5.53%	7.84%	1.62%	1.32%	26.94%
Channel3	-0.70%	1.21%	1.38%	1.52%	2.08%	3.15%	5.21%	7.01%	1.40%	1.09%	23.36%
Channel4	1.56%	1.59%	1.35%	1.42%	1.70%	2.68%	4.26%	5.81%	1.37%	1.02%	22.77%
	1.86%	5.46%	5.52%	6.30%	8.39%	13.13%	21.10%	27.67%	5.89%	4.68%	100.00%
FLEXIBLE											
	Main openings								Small openings		Total
left	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	up	down	Total
Channel1	-0.40%	1.54%	1.52%	1.71%	2.22%	3.45%	5.48%	7.31%	1.16%	1.14%	25.14%
Channel2	-0.35%	1.75%	1.57%	1.65%	2.16%	3.30%	5.28%	7.41%	1.18%	1.15%	25.10%
Channel3	-0.05%	1.68%	1.57%	1.68%	2.13%	3.24%	5.11%	7.17%	1.19%	1.14%	24.85%
Channel4	1.28%	1.95%	1.57%	1.63%	2.01%	2.97%	4.72%	6.60%	1.11%	1.06%	24.91%
	0.48%	6.93%	6.23%	6.67%	8.53%	12.96%	20.59%	28.48%	4.64%	4.49%	100.00%

Table 4 Split 3 Right

RIGID											
	Main openings								Small openings		
right	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	up	down	Total
Channel1	0.77%	1.36%	1.42%	1.65%	2.38%	3.91%	6.17%	7.20%	1.53%	1.25%	27.64%
Channel2	-0.27%	1.36%	1.46%	1.61%	2.17%	3.39%	5.38%	7.25%	1.49%	1.19%	25.02%
Channel3	-0.37%	1.62%	1.34%	1.41%	1.87%	2.95%	4.79%	5.93%	1.30%	1.03%	21.88%
Channel4	1.68%	1.91%	1.46%	1.55%	1.93%	2.97%	4.68%	6.62%	1.50%	1.15%	25.46%
	1.81%	6.25%	5.68%	6.22%	8.36%	13.21%	21.02%	27.00%	5.82%	4.63%	100.00%
FLEXIBLE											
	Main openings								Small openings		
right	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	up	down	Total
Channel1	-0.33%	1.74%	1.54%	1.72%	2.18%	3.37%	5.33%	7.43%	1.14%	1.11%	25.23%
Channel2	-0.36%	1.60%	1.55%	1.72%	2.21%	3.40%	5.39%	7.49%	1.19%	1.18%	25.36%
Channel3	0.30%	1.69%	1.43%	1.65%	2.10%	3.23%	5.16%	7.31%	0.69%	1.11%	24.67%
Channel4	1.34%	1.76%	1.47%	1.55%	1.96%	3.04%	4.84%	6.63%	1.04%	1.12%	24.74%
	0.96%	6.78%	5.98%	6.64%	8.45%	13.03%	20.72%	28.86%	4.06%	4.53%	100.00%

The total pressure drop between inlet and outlet is 28.1 Pa for the rigid ducts and 422.1 Pa for the flexible ducts.

The average pressure drop (Table 5) is calculated at different sections, with the nomenclature previously described in paragraph 3.1.1 (Figure 9, Figure 10, Figure 11, Figure 13), with the objective of checking losses across each branch:

- ΔP_1 : before the branches and inlet
- ΔP_{2b} : due to the flow rate valves
- ΔP_2 : after and before the branches
- ΔP_3 : outlet and after the branches

Table 5 Pressure Drops

	RIGID	FLEXIBLE
ΔP_1	4.6	4.1
ΔP_{2b}	-	286.2
ΔP_2	10.1	123.1
ΔP_3	13.4	8.6
Total ΔP	28.1	422.1

The curve of the valve used in the simulation with flexible ducts is reported in Figure 14. The average velocity at the valve is 12.6 m/s, which leads to a pressure drop of 286.2 Pa. The valve working point is highlighted in red.

Figure 14 Valve curve and working point

The unbalanced mass flow distribution reported in Table 3 and Table 4 is confirmed also by the velocity contour in the normal direction, with respect to the louvers. In Figure 15, normal velocity is reported for both configurations. The louvers on the left side of the picture suck in air, while the louvers on the right blow air with a velocity that can reach 3 m/s. To generally decrease the average velocity on the louvers, an increment of the area for these sections is proposed. This modification has been implemented and studied in section 3.2.

Figure 15 Velocity (normal direction) at outlet of right channel. Left: rigid ducts. Right: flexible ducts

In the following figures, the velocity contour is represented at two cut planes, one horizontal and one vertical. The behavior of the velocity is qualitatively the same at other sections. From these pictures, it is possible to observe the penetration of the flow coming out from the louvers. Figure 16 regards the base case with rigid ducts, but an analogous profile was found for the scenario with flexible ducts. The behavior of the small holes can also be observed in Figure 17, especially the first ones close to the channel bend and the last ones. These holes show a difference between flexible and rigid ducts, especially at the beginning of the channel.

Figure 16 Velocity contour at horizontal plane, rigid ducts

Figure 17 Velocity contour at vertical plane. Left: rigid duct. Right: flexible ducts

In Figure 18, the pressure contour on the horizontal plane (a cut plane at the level of channel 2) shows that in the first part of the horizontal duct the pressure becomes lower than the pressure inside the FEG. For this reason the first louver starts sucking in air from the FEG. This effect can be avoided by optimizing the geometry of the horizontal ducts as implemented in section 3.2. The same occurs in the flexible ducts, although not reported in the figure since it is analogous.

Figure 18 Relative pressure contour at horizontal plane

After these simulations the following conclusions apply for the two configurations:

- There is a good distribution at splits 1 and 2: air is uniformly divided into the different branches
- At each channel, there is a high mass flow at the last main openings
- Small openings have a variable behavior depending on whether they are positioned at the top/bottom part and beginning/end of the channel
- Recirculation zones are formed at the beginning of the horizontal channels. In this case pressure is locally lower than the FEG pressure and air is sucked into the ducts through the first louvers
- The velocity can reach 3 m/s at some louvers.

Therefore the 2 possibilities have a similar qualitative behavior.

The difference is in the pressure drops (Table 5), since the addition of the valves increases this drop. In the configuration with the flexible channels, the total pressure drop increases for 2 reasons: pressure drop due to the valves: 286.2 Pa and pressure drop due to the geometrical changes. Changing from 8 channels to 16 tubes the pressure drop is 123.1 Pa instead of 10.1 Pa.

The configuration with flexible ducts and valves allows the regulation of the flow with the valves: this possibility makes the mass flow split more controllable even if the pressure loss is higher.

3.2 Single horizontal duct

In this section, detailed analyses are performed to optimize the shape of the 8 horizontal ducts with louvers. Comparing the result obtained at the 8 horizontal ducts (section 3.1.2), the mass flow distribution on the louvers is similar. For this reason the geometrical optimization takes into account only one horizontal ducts, because it is representative of all horizontal ducts.

In the following paragraphs three geometrical configurations are proposed and discussed.

3.2.1 Geometrical configurations

The original geometry is reported in Figure 19, where the channel is updated and has new opening area of the louvers and a new shape. There are two bends at the beginning in order to match with the new configuration of the FEG and SS. The louver area is increased in order to have a higher mass flow and a smaller velocity across the plants. The width of the channel is 78 mm and small holes are placed near the FEG wall, following the duct shape (Figure 20).

Figure 19 Geometry 1

Figure 20 Holes and louvers

A second geometry with variable width has been created. The initial width is 64 mm and it becomes smaller moving towards the end of the duct. In the middle it measures 34 mm and at the end 14 mm in width. This configuration is proposed in order to decrease the mass flow of the last louvers. Small holes (up and down part of the channel) are placed near the louvers according to the duct shape. At the beginning of the duct in Figure 22, the holes start after the two bends. At the last two louvers the space is not enough to

perforate the channel with holes, therefore they are interrupted at the seventh louver as shown in Figure 23. The blue color in Figure 21, Figure 22 and Figure 23 show the parts of the channels that are blocked to the flow passage.

Figure 21 Geometry 2

Figure 22 Geometry 2: Beginning part

Figure 23 Geometry 2: End part

The third geometry was built taking into account the manufacturing aspect for a duct to have a variable decreasing width. The duct now is formed by assembling 4 pieces with decreasing width (78.5, 60, 45.5 and 12.5 mm), rather than taking a duct with uniform width and placing inserts inside the duct to decrease the effective width as in the second geometry.

Figure 24 Geometry 3

Figure 25 Geometry 3: top view

3.2.2 Results

A comparison between these 3 solutions is performed. In Figure 26 the mass flow is represented, noticing that in the first configuration air is flowing into the duct through the first louver and the mass flow is completely unbalanced. The final geometry shows a better mass flow distribution, compared to the initial one, but some differences among the louvers are still present. A more detailed comparison appears in Figure 27 with all the solutions put together.

Figure 26 Results: from top to bottom, mass flow in Geometry 1, 2 and 3

Table 6 Mass Flow and standard deviation of mass flow at openings

VOLUMETRIC FLOW [m ³ /h]	OUT1	OUT2	OUT3	OUT4	OUT5	OUT6	OUT7	OUT 8	Holes UP	Holes DOWN
CONSTANT WIDTH	-8.8	8.7	7.1	6.5	6.5	11.3	28.3	55.2	29.8	30.4
VARIABLE WIDTH	18.0	18.9	15.6	15.6	13.6	19.2	20.1	14.0	19.4	20.5
FINAL GEOMETRY	22.8	31.5	14.0	23.0	14.5	25.0	8.2	15.3	10.4	10.4

Standard deviation of mass flow at openings (louvers) [m ³ /h]	
CONSTANT WIDTH	19.3
VARIABLE WIDTH	2.5
FINAL GEOMETRY	7.5

Figure 27 Mass Flow at openings

The final geometry is a compromise between the geometry 1 and geometry 2. In fact geometry 2 has a variable width over the entire length of the duct: this would imply a customization of the duct leading to higher costs. Geometry 3 changes the width of the duct every two louvers: even though the flow distribution is not optimal, it accounts for constraints on manufacturing and reduces costs.

4 AMS Rack

The AMS is designed to collect the air from the FEG and process it to be supplied again, with a total recirculation system configuration (Figure 28). When the air comes out of the FEG, it has to be filtered (with VOC and HEPA filters), dehumidified (to collect the water produced by plants) and finally heated to adjust its temperature. All these components generate pressure losses which have to be balanced by the fans' head.

For this reasons, in this chapter the part of the AMS that is dedicated to the air treatment is simulated. The aim is to verify the pressure losses of the entire AMS loop and to calculate the air mass flow provided by the fans. Simulations were performed for the initial layout, shown below, and subsequently for an updated configuration.

Figure 28 Initial layout of the AMS Rack

4.1 Initial Configuration

4.1.1 Geometry, mesh and boundary conditions

The geometrical model is reported in Figure 29, where all the AMS components are indicated. The outflow duct is dedicated to the collection of the air coming from the FEG. On the contrary the inflow duct provides fresh air to the FEG.

Figure 29 Initial geometry of the AMS Rack

Figure 30 Equivalent circuit and extrusion of duct section

A new subdomain called “equivalent circuit” (Figure 30) is added at the outlet: this domain assumes the same pressure loss of the entire air distribution channels which were previously studied in section 3.1.2 (geometry with flexible ducts).

Figure 31 Boundary conditions

The simulated fluid is air, treated as an ideal gas. The flow is in turbulent condition, isothermal and in a steady state. Boundary conditions are represented in Figure 31, where Inlet (red) and Outlet (yellow) have the same atmospheric pressure: in fact both the inlet and outlet of this model are virtually in contact with the same environment (FEG), which is assumed to be at 1 atm. An extrusion of the duct section is created to keep the outlet far from any subdomains (Figure 30). At the outlet side wall (blue in Figure 31) a free slip condition is imposed: in this way no additional pressure losses are added on the extrusion section.

ANSYS
R16.1

Figure 32 Fan positions

The two fans, shown in Figure 32, are chosen from the Ebmpapst catalogue [1] and they are modeled with the corresponding momentum source (curve B in Figure 33).

Figure 33 Fan curve

Figure 34 Filters, dehumidifier and heaters treated as porous media

Filters, dehumidifier and heater in Figure 34 are modeled as porous media with a specified pressure loss curve as reported in Figure 35. These characteristic curves have been provided by AS. The curve related to the equivalent circuit has been calculated from the simulation results obtained in section 3.1.2 (geometry with flexible ducts).

Figure 35 Porous media curve

4.1.2 Results

The calculated mass flow which fits to the combined pressure losses of all the components is 1226 m³/h. The working point position, on the filter and fan curves, is reported in Figure 36.

Figure 36 Working point of the circuit

The detailed pressure drops are reported in Figure 36, referring to the names described in Figure 29: The total pressure loss of the AMS system is 2195 Pa, which is primary composed by the HEPA filter and the geometric losses. The necessary pressure head (2195 Pa) is equally split between the two fans which provide a mass flow = 1226 m³/h and a pressure head of around 1100 Pa per fan. Pressure losses are caused by filters, humidifier, heater and the equivalent circuit which are added to the pressure loss due to the geometry.

Table 7 Pressure Drops

Component	ΔP [Pa]
HEPA filter	455
VOC filter	144
Dehumidifier	116
Heater	191
Filter out	80
Equivalent circuit	334
Geometric losses	875
Total	2195

The resulting mass flow through the circuit does not reach the intended one of 1400 m³/h, in fact it is lower, i.e. 1226 m³/h.

4.2 Updated configuration

The original configuration, as presented in the previous section, did not allow the selected fans to deliver the desired flow rate. As such, a number of options were considered to reduce the system pressure losses, thereby allowing for an increase in the overall flow rate.

The updated configuration of the AMS rack, as well as the related CFD simulation results are presented below.

4.2.1 Geometry, mesh and boundary conditions

The initial configuration was changed in a number of ways, in order to reduce the pressure losses in the system. Specifically, the repositioning of the dehumidifier and the first main fan allowed for an adjustment in the ducting which was considered to be superior to the previous design.

Additionally, a change was made to the ducting connecting to and from the filters, with the added change of an inclusion of a pre-filter to increase the operational lifetime of the HEPA filter. Lastly, the heater which was originally modelled as a porous media has been updated to reflect the actual geometry, to better assess the actual pressure loss as a result of this component.

The updated configuration of the AMS rack can be seen in Figure 37.

Figure 37 Updated geometry of AMS Rack

The same boundary conditions were applied for the updated AMS rack simulations as for the initial simulations.

As the actual heater geometry was taken into account, it was no longer modelled as a porous media as in the previous simulations. The added pre-filter however was modelled as a porous media, similar to the other filters, with the characteristic curve supplied by AS.

4.2.2 Results

The main difference between the initial configuration and the updated configuration results from a reduction in the geometric pressure losses. The different sections of the geometry which were simulated to determine the overall pressure losses are shown in Figure 38.

Figure 38 Duct sections for geometric pressure loss determination

The pressure losses for each of these sections can be found in Table 8. These pressure losses were determined at the fan working point, which balances the fan pressure heads with the component and geometric pressure losses.

As seen in Table 9, which indicates the pressure losses in the old and new configuration for a flow rate of 1400 m³/h, the geometric pressure losses were reduced by 792 Pa, or approximately 70% of the old value. Also note that the pressure losses due to the heater elements were significantly reduced by modeling the actual geometry, as opposed to modeling the heater as a porous media.

Table 8 Geometric pressure losses (at a flow rate of 1458 m³/h)

Geometric losses		ΔP [Pa]
1	Filter Out – Dehumidifier In	18
2	Dehumidifier Out – Heater In	3
3	Heater Out – Fan In	67
4	Fan Out – Prefilter In	135
5	VOC Out – Fan 2 In	76
6	Fan 2 Out – Circuit In	65
7	Other duct losses	9
Total		373

Table 9 AMS configuration pressure loss comparison (at a flow rate of 1400 m³/h)

Component	Pressure loss	
	Old	New
Pre-filter	-	62
HEPA filter	600	600
VOC filter	200	200
Dehumidifier	150	150
Heater	240	1,3
Equivalent Circuit	422	422
Geometric Loss	1137	345

The actual working point flow rate for the new AMS configuration is 1458 m³/h. Note that this is the worst case conditions, where the pressure drops over the filters are assumed to be much higher as a result of filter clogging. As such, with new, clean, filters the achievable flow rate will be even higher.

As the updated configuration meets the target flow rate of 1400 m³/h even in the worst case conditions, no further major design changes were needed.

5 Future Exploration Greenhouse

In this chapter the simulations regarding the FEG are presented. The objective is to characterize the flow and temperature inside the greenhouse in order to avoid stagnation points and recirculation zones. It is necessary to have a uniform temperature distribution, reducing the temperature gradients to the minimal values. Furthermore, the temperature and RH around the plants are monitored.

In this chapter three different simulations will be presented. The first scenario is “summer day”, i.e. when the external temperature reaches its maximum (5 °C) and all the internal devices are switched on and are working. This setting represents an extreme condition; therefore it gives important information about the problems which can occur in a worst case scenario. This hot case scenario will be simulated both with and without plants, to reflect, respectively, the steady state operating phase and the initial start-up phase.

The third simulation which will be discussed is the extreme cold scenario, assuming steady state operating phase with fully mature plants. In this case, the external temperature is assumed to be -50 °C and the internal heat load is reduced to reflect the night cycle of the plant cultivation process.

For each of the aforementioned simulations, two configurations are simulated and compared: a baseline design and a second case with the introduction of internal fans. The configuration with additional circulation fans was defined in order to improve the air mixing inside the FEG compared to the baseline design.

Figure 39 FEG layout with internal fans

5.1 Summer day – with plants

5.1.1 Geometry and mesh

The geometry of the baseline design is reported in Figure 40, where some simplifications are applied in order to extract the fluid domain relevant for CFD.

Figure 40 FEG Geometry

In the modified configuration 8 tangential fans are introduced to push air downwards (Figure 41). Fans are mounted on the ceiling as shown in Figure 42.

Figure 41 Tangential fans

Figure 42 Position of fans

For both geometrical models, hybrid meshes (tetrahedral and prisms) are generated leading to mesh dimensions of 40 million elements. Mesh refinement is defined at air inlet sections (Figure 43) and prisms are added on the walls to capture the boundary layer.

Figure 43 Mesh refinement at air inlet sections

5.1.2 Physical model and boundary conditions

For both configurations the boundary conditions are applied as follows. The total mass flow at the inlets is $1400 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, which is the target AMS working point as reported in chapter 4. This model places the inlets at the end of the supply air channels (louvers and small holes of horizontal ducts), as described in section 3.2. At the main inlets (blue sections in Figure 44) a uniform velocity equal to 0.4 m/s is imposed: this value is applied to each louver section and it allows maintaining a max velocity of 0.2 m/s to 0.25 m/s close to the plants. Hence the mass flow from the main inlets is set to $1180 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$. The remaining amount is split across the small openings (up and down), as shown in Figure 45. The inlet air temperature is set to $20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and the relative humidity is 70%.

Figure 44 Main Inlets and outlet

The holes at the upper part of the ducts are replaced with a rectangular opening with an equivalent area (red surface in Figure 45). This operation is done to avoid high refinement of the mesh at the circular holes which would lead to high computational costs. The results will not be affected by this modification since the local velocity will not be altered due to this substitution.

Figure 45 Up and down openings

One single outlet is positioned at the central top part of the FEG (green in Figure 44): an atmospheric pressure is set at this boundary.

Heat sources are assigned to the pumps in the lower part of the FEG (Figure 46):

- Pumps type 1: 8 pressure pumps with a total energy source equal to 40 W
- Pumps type 2: 2 sump pumps with a total energy source equal to 14.4 W

The presence of the heat due to the sun appears as a global domain source: 110 W are estimated considering the heat transfer coefficient of the material, the solar intensity and sun inclination [6][7].

Figure 46 Pumps

Plants are divided into tall, short, cucumber and germination as shown in Figure 47, with respectively different volumes of evapotranspiration. All the plants are considered at their maximum level of growth. For this reason they are modeled as porous media with the following characteristics:

- Resistance Loss Coefficient: 85% of each box is occupied by plants
- Maximum Water Production rate is equal to 2050 g/h
- Energy sink due to plant transpiration is equal to 1392 W (product of maximum water production rate and enthalpy of evaporation at local temperature)

Figure 47 Plants subdivision

Table 10 Water production and energy sink for plant type

Plant type	Number of plants	Total volume [m3]	Energy sink [W]	Water production [g/h]
Short	8	1.21	260.7	383.9
Tall	8	3.72	797.6	1174.6
Germination	3	0.46	97.8	144.0
Cucumber	1	1.10	235.9	347.5
	Total	6.48	1392	2050

Regarding the thermal properties of the walls (Figure 48), the selected materials, thickness and thermal conductivity are reported in Table 11. For each wall a heat transfer coefficient (HTC), with a 10% safety margin is calculated and applied. An external temperature of 5 °C is selected for the walls which are faced with the external environment and 20 °C for the wall and door which separate the FEG and the Service Section.

Figure 48 Walls

Table 11 HTC at walls

Walls	Material	Thickness [m]	Thermal conductivity [W/(m*K)]	Material	Thickness [m]	Thermal conductivity [W/(m*K)]	HTC [W/m ² K]	HTC [W/m ² K] + Safety 10%
Floor	Polyuteran Foam	0.12	0.023	Steel	0.003	47	0.19	0.21
Lateral	Polyuteran Foam	0.08	0.023	Steel	0.003	47	0.29	0.32
Wall FEG-SS	Wood panel	0.02	0.081	Air	0.03	0.0243	0.67	0.74
Door FEG-SS	Wood panel	0.02	0.081	Air	0.03	0.0243	0.67	0.74
Emergency door	Polyuteran Foam	0.12	0.023	Steel	0.003	47	0.19	0.21

The main heat source inside the FEG is due to the light of the LEDs. According to Figure 49 LEDs are divided into short, tall, cucumber and germination depending on the plants they are illuminating: the total power for each plant type is reported in Table 12.

Table 12 LED total power

Description	Panel Intensity On Canopy [umol/m ² /s]	Power per panel [W]	Number of panels	Total power [W]
Tall crops	600	249	9	2241
Short crops	300	124	8	992
Germination	150	62	3	186
Backlight Cucumber	600	249	1	249
			Total	3668

The total LED power is split in different parts:

- 50% is dissipated by the water cooling system (not included in the simulation)
- 25% is applied as radiative heat flux
- 25% is applied as convective heat flux

Figure 49 Position of LEDs

In the second simulation 8 fans are added to the model, keeping the same boundary conditions which have just been presented. Figure 50 shows the simplified model of the fans: they suck air from the top part of the FEG and blow air towards the floor. In this model each fan is supposed to work at a flow rate set point of $300 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ in order to move enough air, and each fan has a heat production of around 70 W [5].

Figure 50 Fans details: inlet and outlet sections

5.1.3 Results

The results are presented, comparing the two configurations to have a clear view of the differences:

- Baseline design called “FEG without fans”
- Update design called “FEG with fans”

The heat balance is reported in Table 13 for both analyses. There is a sink due to plant transpiration, which absorbs 1382 W. The other sink is due to dissipation across the walls, due to the temperature gradient between the internal and the external environment, which generates a heat loss of 229 W. On the other hand, heat production is due to LEDs, pumps and sun.

For both cases the total balance is positive: the only difference is due to the heat generated by fans.

Table 13 Heat Balance

	FEG without fans Heat [W]	FEG with fans Heat [W]
Heat from LED into the air	1834	1834
Heat absorbed by plant transpiration	-1392	-1392
Heat from pumps type 1	40	40
Heat from pumps type 2	14.4	14.4
Heat from sun	110	110
Heat from Tangential fans	0	560
Heat dissipated through walls	-229	-229
Heat balance	378	938

Considering the heat balance of 378 W and a mass flow of 1400 m³/h, we have an estimated temperature gradient of 0.8 °C between inlet and outlet sections for the baseline design. For the simulation with fans the expected temperature gradient is around 2 °C.

To check the velocity, temperature and relative humidity distribution inside the FEG, monitor planes are defined as represented in Figure 51: there are two YZ-planes and three XZ-planes.

Figure 51 Reference planes

In the following images the nomenclature “without fans” refers to the baseline design, while “with fans” refers to the solution with fans. The same reference planes defined in Figure 49 are considered for the post-processing.

Figure 52 Temperature on plane y1

In the comparison of Figure 52 at the plane y1, the temperature contour is presented, showing a high vertical temperature gradient inside the FEG without fans. In this case hot air (mainly due to LED) moves to the top and cold air (mainly due to plant transpiration) stays near the floor. Hot air accumulates at the ceiling, reaching a temperature of 25 °C: the effects of natural convection and stratification are dominant in this case. A global temperature gradient between 13°C and 25°C is present.

In the simulation with fans, temperature near the ceiling decreases from 25°C to 22 °C, while inside the canopy the temperature increases from 13°C to 16 °C. In this case the temperature gradient is highly reduced and local hot spots are present only close to the LED.

Figure 53 Temperature on plane y2 (corridor)

In Figure 53 the cut plane y2 at the corridor is shown. In the baseline design the air collected by the suction duct is at 20.7 °C, corresponding to the estimated temperature difference between inlet and outlet. Nevertheless, a high temperature gradient still remains in the FEG. Despite the suction effect caused by the return duct, hot air still accumulates at the ceiling due to natural convection.

In the simulation with fans, the temperature at the outlet changes from 20.7 °C (baseline design) to 21.8 °C. This is caused by the addition of the heat of the fans. In this case a better mixing is shown in the corridor: temperature distribution is uniform and stable at 22 °C.

At plane y3, in Figure 54, the temperature distribution is similar to Figure 52: with the fans, the heat accumulation close to the ceiling is avoided. Also in Figure 55 and Figure 56, at plane x1 and x2, the temperature is more uniform, except for air close to the LEDs and some local cold points at the plants. In fact, the presence of plants produces a relevant reduction of velocity that can't guarantee an optimal air mixing. However, the temperature gradient near the plants is reduced by introducing the fans. Moreover when plants are not fully grown the effect of air mixing due to fans in these zones is emphasized.

Figure 54 Temperature on plane y3.

Figure 55 Temperature on plane x1

Figure 56 Temperature on plane x2

In Figure 57, relative humidity reaches 100% for both analyses: air enters in the FEG at RH equal to 70% and this value is probably too high considering the actual amount of water produced by plant. In the FEG with fans, the better air mixing helps to reduce the RH gradient.

Figure 57 Relative humidity on plane y1

In Figure 58, the velocity contour at plane y1 is presented: plants occupy a big part of FEG volume, so when air penetrates the porous media, the velocity is reduced. In Figure 59 the velocity contour and vectors is shown at the corridor. In the simulation with fans the air direction is not only forced by the suction effect at outlet section: a general movement is present due to the additional mixing coming from the fans.

Figure 58 Velocity on plane y1

Figure 59 Velocity on plane y2 (corridor)

Figure 60 Velocity on plane x2

The penetration of the fan injection can be noticed in Figure 60, where air is pushed downwards reaching the floor.

A number is assigned to each plant for post-processing purposes, as shown in Figure 61. The volume average of temperature and RH for each plant domain is computed and reported in Table 14.

Figure 61 Plants numbering

Table 14 Plant temperatures

Plants number	Temperature °C (FEG)	Temperature °C (FEG with fans)	RH (FEG)	RH (FEG with fans)
1	18.2	20.8	85.4 %	72.5%
2	17.8	20.8	89.9%	74.4%
3	17.6	20.6	94.3%	74.9%
4	19.0	21.4	82.9%	69.1%
5	19.6	20.8	80.1%	68.7%
6	20.0	21.6	79.6%	70.0%
7	16.7	20.1	100%	79.4%
8	19.4	21.4	80.5%	69.0%
9	19.9	21.9	78.9%	68.9%
10	19.9	21.6	82.3%	70.1%
11	16.3	20.1	100%	79.2%
12	18.8	21.0	84.0%	74.7%
13	16.1	17.7	100%	93.0%
14	17.7	20.8	90.9%	77.1%
15	16.8	18.3	98.5%	90.0%
16	17.6	19.1	93.7%	86.1%
17	17.8	20.8	90.8%	76.4%
18	16.6	18.6	100%	88.2%
19	18.8	20.8	84.4%	75.4%
20	16.2	18.2	100%	90.5%

Table 15 Average and standard deviation for temperature on reference planes

TEMPERATURE [C]		FEG	FEG with fans
Plane y1	Average [C]	18.4	19.3
	Standard Deviation [C]	2.9	2.1
Plane y2 (corridor)	Average [C]	19.2	21.6
	Standard Deviation [C]	1.8	1.0
Plane y3	Average [C]	19.3	20.5
	Standard Deviation [C]	2.8	1.9
Plants	Average [C]	17.7	19.8
	Standard Deviation [C]	2.1	1.9

Table 16 Average and standard deviation for RH on reference planes

RH [%]		FEG	FEG with fans
Plane y1	Average	89.4%	84.6%
	Standard Deviation	19.2%	12.8%
Plane y2 (corridor)	Average	86.3%	69.6%
	Standard Deviation	13.1%	5.2%
Plane y3	Average	84.5%	75.3%
	Standard Deviation	20.6%	10.8%
Plants	Average	93.6%	80.9%
	Standard Deviation	17.7%	12.0%

In Table 15 and Table 16, statistical quantities (average and standard deviation) for temperature and RH are calculated at the reference planes and at the plant domains. In particular these two tables show an increment of average temperature and a consequent reduction of RH in the simulation with fans. Moreover the standard deviation of these quantities is decreased with the introduction of fans: this is due a better air mixing which reduces the gradients of temperature and RH. This improvement is emphasized in the corridor where the velocity is higher.

In conclusion, adding the fans positively affects the temperature, RH and velocity distribution: in this case air is better mixed, resulting in more uniform conditions inside the FEG.

5.2 Summer day – without plants

During the initial start-up phase of the MTF the plants will be at a juvenile stage of their development, which means the plants do not yet impede the flow coming from the horizontal air ducts. Additionally, the plant transpiration will be significantly lower in this phase, and it is neglected in this simulation, along with the corresponding cooling effect.

The boundary conditions and the mesh are the same as in the previous case, aside from the plant volumes which have been removed.

Qualitatively the simulation results are similar to the previous scenario, except for the air flow and air mixing in the plant cultivation racks, see Figure 62. Since the obstructions from the plant volumes have been removed, the air flow easily penetrates into the racks.

Quantitatively, the lack of transpiration and associated cooling results in a higher temperature throughout the FEG. To counteract this, as well as to allow for control of the humidity during this phase, a standalone humidifier will be installed (temporarily) in the FEG in the initial operations phase.

Figure 62 Velocity on plane x1 – no plants

5.3 Winter night

5.3.1 Boundary conditions

This scenario provides an extreme condition, reflecting the worst case cold scenario.

The following boundary conditions have been altered with respect to the ‘summer day’ scenarios:

- The outside temperature has been reduced from 5 ° to -50 °C
- The Service Section temperature has been reduced from 20 °C to 18 °C
- The sump pumps are assumed to be off
- The Sun thermal load is removed
- Water production rate has been reduced to 385 g/h, resulting in a cooling load of 261 W
- The LED panels are assumed to be off

The resulting heat balance for this scenario can be seen in Table 17.

Considering a heat balance of -885W and a mass flow of 1400 m³/h, we have an estimated temperature gradient of -1.9 °C between inlet and outlet for the configuration without fans. The added heat from the fans results in an estimated temperature gradient of -0.7 °C

Table 17 Heat balance – Winter night

	FEG without fans Heat [W]	FEG with fans Heat [W]
Heat from LED into the air	0	0
Heat absorbed by plant transpiration	-261	-261
Heat from pumps type 1	40	40
Heat from pumps type 2	0	0
Heat from sun	0	0
Heat from Tangential fans	0	560
Heat dissipated through walls	-664	-664
Heat balance	-885	-325

The same mesh and monitoring planes are used as in the summer day simulations. Qualitatively, the results are similar with the configuration with fans resulting in a better air distribution inside the FEG.

The main design aspects which are of interest in this scenario are the risk of condensation on the walls, and the interaction between the sub-floor area and the main area. Figure 63 illustrates the velocity on monitoring plane x1 for the configurations without (left) and with fans (right). Note that there is basically no air flow at the bottom of the FEG in the sub-floor area. This results in the air in the sub-floor area being significantly colder than the air above the floor. Furthermore, note the reduced air flow near the ducts, in particular the lower two horizontal ducts on both sides. Based on the simulation results, these spots are most likely to have condensation occurring during the operations phase of the MTF.

Figure 63 Velocity on plane x1

Based on the results of this simulation, an adjustment was made to the FEG floor design. The panels on either side of the corridor have been removed to allow more interaction between the sub-floor air and the main area. Furthermore, a sub-floor space heater has been installed to prevent the air in the sub-floor area from dropping below a set temperature.

The risk of condensation on the walls will be monitored during operations in the Antarctic. Mitigation of any condensation will be done by adjusting the FEG operating set points and adding local insulation material on cold spots. A thermal camera will be used to investigate the wall temperatures.

6 Failure scenario for the Mobile Test Facility

This section describes the simulations regarding a possible failure scenario for the MTF. In case of a breakdown of some part of the air management system (especially air heaters and fans), the internal desired temperature cannot be maintained. In this situation, due to the rigid temperature of the external environment (between $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $+5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), the MTF cools down until the normal operating conditions are restored.

The aim of this model is to estimate the cooling down time of the MTF and correlate it to the external climatic conditions. Different wind velocities and temperatures are considered according to the measurements recorded at Neumayer III Antarctic station [3][6].

6.1 Geometry and mesh

The geometrical model is created representing the MTF as a box and placing it in a portion of the external environment. Hence the model is composed of two domains (Figure 64):

1. The MTF (dimensions = $2.438\text{ m} \times 2.895\text{ m} \times 12.116\text{ m}$), which is positioned above the ground (the wind is free to flow below the floor of the MTF)
2. An external air box (dimensions = $14.5\text{ m} \times 12.2\text{ m} \times 60.6\text{ m}$), which contains the MTF

Figure 64 Left: External preliminary design of MTF. Right: Geometrical model (MTF and external air box)

The computational mesh is fully composed of hexahedral elements and it is especially refined near the surface of MTF for an accurate calculation of heat transfer between the external and the internal domain. The mesh is composed of 3.5 million elements.

Figure 65 Mesh of the two computational domains (MTF and external air box)

6.2 Physical model and boundary conditions

The two computational domains are filled with air, which is treated as an ideal gas. The interface between the two domains is a wall with the physical properties of polyurethane foam (Density=32 kg/m³, Thermal conductivity =0.023 W/m K, Specific Heat=1500 J/Kg K) and a thickness of 8 cm. The selection of the isolating material and thickness has been defined according to a preliminary design of the MTF (Figure 66).

Figure 66 Materials for the different domains

The external domain has one inlet section, where wind speed and temperature are specified, and one outlet section, where atmospheric pressure is imposed (Figure 67). Four different scenarios (called simulation 1-4) are performed considering combinations of three wind temperatures and two wind speeds as reported in Table 18.

According to the boundary conditions, the flow is fully turbulent. Before solving each thermal transient scenario, steady state analyses are carried out to evaluate the pressure and velocity fields around the MTF. Then the energy equation is solved with transient analyses to calculate the temperature evolution inside the MTF. Each transient scenario starts by fixing the temperature inside the MTF at 22 °C. Each simulation stops when the air inside the MTF reaches 5 °C.

Table 18 Inlet boundary conditions

	Wind speed [m/s]	Wind temperature[°C]
SIMULATION 1	30	-50
SIMULATION 2	30	-30
SIMULATION 3	30	-10
SIMULATION 4	10	-30

To sum up, this model takes into account the external air, the insulating material of the MTF and the presence of stagnant air inside: the internal detailed design of the MTF can be neglected for the calculation of the cooling time.

Figure 67 Inlet and outlet sections

6.3 Results

Each simulation points out the temperature decay from 22 °C to 5 °C for the MTF: the temperature behavior, and consequently the cooling time, for simulation 1 is reported in Figure 68. In this way all the cooling times are collected for the simulation 1-4 and shown in Table 19.

Figure 68 Temperature evolution of MTF for Simulation 1

Table 19 Cooling time for simulation 1-4

	Wind speed [m/s]	Wind temperature [°C]	Time needed to reach 5[°C] from 22[°C] for the MTF [minutes]
SIMULATION 1	30	-50	49
SIMULATION 2	30	-30	79
SIMULATION 3	30	-10	184
SIMULATION 4	10	-30	80

Looking at simulation 2 and 4, in Table 19, the cooling time is really similar: this fact reveals that the variation of wind speed does not have a relevant influence on the cooling time. This is probably due to the thickness and the thermal properties of the isolating material.

In simulations 1 and 3, the variation of wind temperature produces significant changes for the cooling time. For example when the wind temperature is -10 °C (simulation 3), the cooling time of the MTF is around 184 min, which is more than 3 times the value obtained when the external temperature is -50 °C. The relation between cooling time and wind temperature is shown in Figure 69.

Figure 69 Cooling time and wind temperature

7 Conclusions

This report summarizes the simulation process which was carried out for the layout of the MTF and some of its relevant systems. In particular, CFD analyses have guided the optimization procedure of the preliminary facility design which has been firstly designed during the CE weeks (Bremen, from September 7th to September 18th 2015).

During this work package CFD analyses have been carried out with the following main objective: ensure the proper climate conditions for plant growth (meaning homogeneous temperature, RH and velocity). For this reason, special attention has been paid to the AMS layout, its sub-systems and its relationship with the design of the FEG. Both internal and external variables are taken into account to evaluate the local comfort inside the FEG: LED lights, transpiration of the plants, relative humidity, type of insulating material and external environmental conditions.

The main conclusions and recommendations for each designed subsystem are reported below.

In chapter 3 the supply air channels of the AMS have been investigated. Two configurations are compared: one with rigid ducts and one with flexible ducts (section 3.1). The solution with flexible ducts presents higher pressure losses compared to the rigid ducts, but it includes a set of regulating valves which allows a more controllable split of the mass flow at this level of the duct. These simulations also reveal the necessity of a geometrical revision of the horizontal ducts that directly provide air into the FEG. Starting from the original geometry, a final characterization of the design has been pointed out. In this case a better mass flow balance has been obtained by reducing the width of the channel along its length (section 3.2).

In chapter 4 the entire AMS circuit has been studied: all the components dedicated to the air treatment are taken into account. The pressure losses within the AMS, and the maximum fan flow rate working point, have been calculated: the estimated mass flow of the initial configuration was 1226 m³/h, which is lower than the desired target (1400 m³/h). As a result, the configuration was altered to reduce the geometric pressure losses. The reduced geometric pressure losses allowed for a different fan working point resulting in a worst case flow rate of 1458 m³/h.

Chapter 5 is dedicated to the thermal comfort analyses of the FEG in a worst case scenario. The study of the baseline has shown high local gradients (from 13 °C to 25°C). This result indicates that there is not enough air mixing inside the FEG. For this reason additional fans have been selected, and positioned at the ceiling. With this solution, a relevant reduction of temperature and RH gradients is registered. Simulations of the start-up phase (without plants), as well as the worst cold case scenario were performed and specific design adjustments were implemented to mitigate any problems.

In chapter 6 the environmental variables (wind speed and temperature) are considered in the case of a failure scenario to understand the thermal inertia of the MTF with respect to the selected insulating material.

In this work package ES, working in close collaboration with DLR and AS, has used CFD analyses to improve the layout of the MTF, highlighting the critical aspects and guiding the design process.

References

- [1] Roccheggiani, "Constant flow manual regulator," 2015. [Online]. Available: <http://www.roccheggiani.it/res/ftproccheggiani/prodotti/centrali-ed-unita-trattamento-aria-hvac-solutions/diffusione-aria/rv/RV.pdf>. [Accessed 29 01 2016].
- [2] Ebmpapst, "RadiPac EC centrifugal fans for air handling units (AHU)," 2015. [Online]. Available: http://www.ebmpapst.com/en/products/centrifugal-fans/radipac/radipac_plugfans.php. [Accessed 29 01 2016].
- [3] AWI Neumayer Station III, "Working and living in the eternal ice - Extreme conditions," 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://www.awi.de/en/expedition/stations/neumayer-station-iii.html>. [Accessed 31 01 2016].
- [4] EDEN ISS, Design Report-v0.1, DLR, WP2.3-D2.5, 2015.
- [5] Ebmpapst, "AC tangential blower," 2015. [Online]. Available: <http://img.ebmpapst.com/products/datasheets/AC-tangential-blower-QLN6530303045-ENG.pdf>. [Accessed 29 01 2016].
- [6] EDEN ISS, Exterior Environmental Conditions-v0.1, DLR, WP2.1, 2015.
- [7] Eugene Stamper, Richard L. Koral "Handbook of Air Conditioning, Heating, and Ventilating" Industrial Press Inc., 1979
- [8] ANSYS, "ANSYS PRODUCTS", [Online]. Available: <http://www.ansys.com/Products> [Accessed 29 01 2016].

